

Kinetics of Interaction between Methanol and Dye-Base of Ethyl Violet in Benzene Medium

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The kinetics of interaction between the dye-base of ethyl violet and methanol has been studied in benzene medium at 35°.

Recently the interaction of organic acids and dye-base of crystal violet in benzene medium has been studied in this laboratory¹. It is interesting, if not unexpected, that the reaction of the alcohols with the dye-base appears to follow the behaviour of "acid-base catalysis" just like the acids. Actually the literature of acid-base reactions in non-aqueous medium involving organic acids is vast, but studies involving alcohols are indeed rare. This prompted us to undertake a systematic study of the kinetics of interaction between the alcohols and the organic dye-base in non-aqueous media. Moreover such studies would give an idea about the association and proton donating capacity of the alcohols.

This communication reports the results of our observations on the interaction between dye-base of ethyl violet and methanol in benzene medium.

EXPERIMENTAL

Analar methanol (BDH.) was distilled before use. The ethyl violet dye was obtained as gift from the Allied Chemical Corp. (National Aniline Division). Dry and thiophene-free benzene kept over sodium wire was used.

Dye-base of ethyl violet was precipitated by adding aqueous alkali to a strong aqueous solution of the dye and was extracted with benzene following the technique developed by Palit². The solid dye-base was then recovered from the benzene extract by removing the solvent using the freeze-drying technique³. The infra-red spectra of the dye-base was obtained in a KBr disc using Perkin Elmer IR Spectrophotometer Model No. 137. The dye-base was found to contain C, 77.8%; H 8.90%; N, 8.48%, Calc. for $C_{21}H_{43}N_3O$: C, 78.59%; H, 9.15%; N, 8.87%.

The variation of optical density with time was recorded with a Hilger UVSPECK photoelectric spectrophotometer at 595 m μ using 1 cm. stoppered silica cells. A special device was used for regulating the temperature in the cell compartment within $\pm 0.2^\circ$.

1. Bhowmik, D. Phil. Thesis "Acid-base reaction in non-aqueous solvents, (with special reference to dyes)" Calcutta University, 1963.

2. Palit, *Chem & Ind.*, 1960, 1531; *Anal. Chem.* 1961, 33, 1441.

3. De and Palit, Unpublished.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Our experimental data are in accord with the following equation (1), for a first order reaction,

$$k = \frac{2.303}{t} \log \frac{x_0}{x_0 - x} \quad (1)$$

where x = O.D. reading at time t , x_0 = O.D. reading at equilibrium and k = the observed rate constant. Values of k were obtained from the plot of $-\log(x_0 - x)$ vs. t . Although k is independent of the dye-base concentration, it strongly depends on the alcohol concentration C . The plot of $-\log(x_0 - x)$ versus t at a given dye-base concentration and at different alcohol concentrations at 35° is shown in Fig. II. The results are summarized in Table I which shows that values of k/c are not constant. Further studies with a variety of alcohols are in progress and until sufficient information is available, any definite conclusion in regard to this type of dependence of rate constant on alcohol concentration is postponed for the present. But it will not be unjustified if this phenomenon is attributed to the association of alcohols and indeed from conductivity measurements in benzene medium it has been shown that association sharply increases above a critical concentration range which is lower than that used in the present work⁴.

FIG. 1

TABLE I

Concentration of Dye-base = $6.01 \times 10^{-6} M$.

$C(M)$	..	0.332	10.560	11.788	13.016	14.244
$k \times 10^3$ (min^{-1})	..	2.027	3.208	5.330	7.218	10.009
$k/c \times 10^3$ ($M^{-1} \text{min}^{-1}$)	..	2.172	3.004	4.525	5.547	7.041

4. Mayaki and Habboush, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1965, 112, 222.

Cryoscopic measurements along with the micro-analysis results show the molecular formula of the dye-base to be $C_{31}H_{43}N_3O$. The IR study of the dye-base in KBr disc shows the presence of OH band. The IR spectra was also recorded in nujol, CS_2 , benzene. We got evidence for the presence of OH group in all cases. All these facts suggest the dye-base to be the carbinol base (II) of the dye (I).

FIG. 2

This carbinol base of the dye reacts with the alcohol (R-OH) giving the complexed species whose absorption spectra is shown in Fig I, but no such reaction is found to occur with the ether (R-OR'), proving that the hydroxylic H takes part in the reaction. Again preliminary observations showed the rate of reaction decrease in the order methanol > ethanol > 1-propanol, the order in which the acidic power of the alcohols decreases.

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